

STUDY OF THE HISTORY OF THE FERGHANA VALLEY IN THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE AND THE SOVIET PERIOD HISTORY OF THE 14th CENTURY

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Abstract

The article analyzes the issue of researching the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period of the Ferghana Valley in the Russian Empire and Soviet historiography. Specific aspects of the study of this issue are considered, while the achieved achievements are recognized, the reasons for some mistakes and shortcomings are disclosed.

Key words: Russian Empire, Soviet period, Ferghana, Amir Temur and the Timurids, M. Ivanin, V.V. Barthold, A. Yu. Yakubovsky, I. M. Mominov, S. A. Azimjonova, O. D. Chekhovich, M. Abduraimov, N. Mahmudov, A. Juvonmardiev, B. G. Gafurov.

The scientific works and research published during the Russian Empire and the Soviet era are also extensive in terms of period and territory [1]. Some Russian historians have briefly touched on the history of the Timurid period in their works on the history of Russia[2]. With the development of oriental studies, separate studies on various issues of the history of the Timurid dynasty appeared[3]. Some notes on the topic under study are found in them. M. In his work dedicated to the military art of Chingiz Khan and Amir Temur, Ivanin talked about the campaigns conducted by the ruler of Turan against the states of Mongolia and the Golden Horde. Several thoughts about the history of the valley are reflected in it. The author writes that the attempt of the Mongol general Anqotara to reach Sirdarya and besiege Andijan was unsuccessful, that during the campaign against them, a part of Amir Temur's army was led by the governor of Fergana region, Mirzo Umarshaikh, and at the end of the campaign, the same military unit returned to Andijan via Kuzan, Uchturfon, Koshghar. M. Although Ivanin correctly indicated the direction of movement of the Timurid army, he ignored the fact that the Mongols under the leadership of Anqotara defeated Mirza Umarshaikh on the banks of the Syr Darya and crossed the river, and came to the wrong conclusion that the Mongols went as far as the Syr Darya.

Among the scientific studies included in the second group, the works of orientalist V.V. Bartold are of great importance due to their scientific value and importance. The author did not conduct a separate research on the history of Fergana Valley during the period of Amir Temur and Timurids. However, in a number of works and articles, he expressed his opinion on this issue [4].

V. V. Bartold, speaking about Amir Temur's military campaign to Mongolia in 1375 in his work "Ocherki istorii Semirechya", noted that he returned from this campaign through the Ferghana Valley. Nizamiddin Shami wrote in his work "Zafarnama" that Amir Temur passed through Yassi region and came to Khojand through the city of Uzgand. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi said that he passed through the Temur Yassi pass and moved along the Uzgand-Khojand route. In this matter, Shami confused Yassi Pass on the way from East Turkestan to Fergana

and Uzgand, the first city after crossing the pass, with Yassi region on the Ettisuv-Tashkent road and Uzgand city on the Syr Darya river. V. V. Bartold made the right decision on this issue based on Yazdi's information. Because at this time, Amir Temur, who was in Otbashi and Arpayozi districts in the southeastern part of Issyk-Kol, returned through Yassi Pass.

There are also some controversial issues in the researches of V. V. Bartold. For example, while talking about the Mongol khan Yunus Khan, the author emphasizes that he tried to capture the Ferghana Valley even before the death of Mirza Sultan Abu Sa'id, but his efforts were unsuccessful, and he relies on Abdurazzoq Samarkandi to justify it. But this information of Abdurazzoq Samarkandi is not found in the works of Mirzo Haydar and Mirzo Babur. Some problems between Mirza Umarshaikh and Yunus Khan happened after the death of Mirza Sultan Abu Said. Therefore, the information of Abdurazzoq Samarkandi is doubtful, and it can be taken as an exaggeration to glorify the governor of Ferghana, Mirza Umarshaikh.

Based on the above information, notes on the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period of the Ferghana Valley taken from the work "Ocherki istorii Semirechya" by V.V.Barthold are mainly of a brief informational character, and issues related to the topic are not researched separately. Also, although some opinions expressed by the author are based on facts available in historical sources, some information and conclusions require a critical approach.

V. V. Bartold in his work "Ulugbek i ego vremya" briefly touched on the issues related to the Fergana Valley. He notes that Ferghana Valley was important as a border region of the Sultanate during the reign of Mirza Umarshaikh and his son Mirza Iskandar. It also draws attention to the fact that the Ferghana Valley was included in one of the two uluses, which were established on the eve of the Chinese campaign and were planned to cover Mongolia as well. He states that as a result of mutual wars that began after the death of Amir Temur, the Ferghana Valley was transferred to the hands of Amir Khudoidad Hosseini. At this point, it is appropriate to mention that these issues have not been extensively analyzed by the author.

While analyzing the issue of the establishment of Mirza Shahrukh's power in Movarounnahr, V.V. Bartold talks a little more widely about the activity of Khudoidad Hosseini, the governor of the Ferghana Valley. The author deeply analyzed the information from historical sources, touched on the capture of Khalil Sultan by Khudoidad, the negotiations between Mirza Shahrukh and the governor of Ferghana. Khudoidad, who sought help from the Mongols, emphasized that it was the Mongols who executed Husayni. Amir mentions that after the destruction of Khudoidad, the Ferghana Valley was given to Mirza Ahmad, the son of Mirza Umarshaikh, and explains that, unlike other princes, Mirza Ahmad reached the age of majority at that time.

The author focuses on the relationship between Timurid princes in the process of covering the termination of Mirzo Ahmad's governorship in the Ferghana Valley by Mirzo Ulug'bek. V.V. Barthold states that the governor of Fergana, who was sent by Mirza Shahrukh to Mirza Ahmad with a yupanchnama, was one of the prisoners captured by Mirza Ulug'bek in the battles in the valley and brought to Herat. However, this servant named Tukul may have been sent to Herat by Mirza Ahmad to congratulate Mirza Shahrukh on his victories in Isfahan, to explain the events that happened to Mirza Ulug'bek, to alleviate the situation, and to ask for help.

The author lists the Ferghana Valley as one of the border regions that were attacked by nomads in the last years of Mirzo Ulug'bek's rule. After that, he spoke briefly about the reign of Mirza Abdulatif, Mirza Abdullah and Mirza Sultan Abu Said.

V. V. Bartold in his work "K istorii oroshenia Turkestana" expressed interesting thoughts about the period of the Fergana Valley that we are studying. Based on the information of "Boburnoma", the author talks about the irrigation system of the valley in this period, types of agricultural crops, horticulture, and concludes that Ferghana during the Timurid period was economically behind Ferghana during the Somonides period. Here, the author relies on the information of Mirza Babur that it is possible to provide an army of 3-4 thousand people with the tax collected from the territory of Ferghana. A comparative analysis of this with the data on economic life reflected in the sources of the Samonite period and the results of archaeological research by V.V. Barthold shows that his ideas are valid.

Speaking about the village of Rabati Sarhang, the author assumes that the village of Koshghar in this city must have appeared at the same time, as it was inhabited by people who were moved from Koshghar by Mirzo Umarshaikh.

In general, V.V. Bartold Amir Temur and the Timurid period in his research on various issues of history recorded certain information about Ferghana Valley. But he did not conduct a special study on this issue and did not study the issue as a whole.

Although research on the history of Amir Temur and the Timurids during the Soviet period achieved some growth in terms of its scope and source enrichment, the ideological patterns of evaluating the historical person and process had a negative impact on the scientific research created during this period. By A.Yu.Yakubovsky, I.M.Mo'minov, S.A.Azimjonova, O.D.Chekhovich, M.Abduraimov, N.Mahmudov, A.Juvonmardiev, B.G.Gofurov In the major research and scientific works devoted to the issues, a number of opinions and conclusions are given regarding the researched topic.

Studies of the Soviet period are analyzed in scientific literature from the point of view of historiography, and the main attention is focused on the period of Amir Temur's rule. In the historiography of this period, A. Yu. Yakubovsky is distinguished by his scientific works on the history of Amir Temur and the Timurid period. At first, in the 70s of the 14th century, he focused on the establishment of Amir Temur's authority in the eastern regions of the Sultanate, and the fact that Fergana was not included in Movarounnahr, which is a khalisa property of the state. Also, some of the historical realities related to Ferghana are briefly covered in other studies by the author [5].

A. Yu. There are also a number of controversial issues in Yakubovsky's research. For example, in historical sources and scientific literature, the Fergana campaign, which was stated to have been carried out by Mirzo Ulugbek in 1414, was recorded by the author as 1413. Also, his opinion that 13 officials served in the palace of Mirza Umarshaikh is also wrong. In this matter, the author relied on the information about 13 beks, which were reflected in the account of the events of the death of Mirza Babur's father. In fact, the analysis of information in "Boburnoma" shows that at this time, under Mirza Umarshaikh, about 20 beks served in various positions.

The work of one of the great Uzbek scientists academician I.M. Mominov "The place and role of Amir Temur in the history of Central Asia" is of special importance. In the author's research, speaking about the role of Amir Temur in the development of his country, he notes that he built caravansary in Movarunnahr regions, including Ferghana [6].

Special scientific researches were also carried out on the era of Mirza Umarshaikh and Mirza Babur, who ruled the Ferghana Valley. One of them is S. "K istorii Fergany vtoroy poloviny XV v" published in 1957 by Azimjonova. is a masterpiece. This work consists of five parts, which

covers the coverage of the reigns of Mirza Umarshaikh and Mirza Babur in historical sources, political and socio-economic issues [7].

The first part of the work is devoted to the analysis of sources illuminating the history of the valley in the second half of the 15th century.

The second part of the study is called "Management of Mirza Umarshaikh". At first, it explained that as a result of mutual wars that started after the death of Mirza Ulughbek, the border regions of Movarunnahr, including the Ferghana Valley, were attacked by nomadic tribes. Based on the information in "History of Rashidi", it is noted that the Mongols made constant raids on the Fergana Valley, Tashkent and Sayram regions from the fortresses in the border areas. The date of Mirza Sultan Abu Sa'id's retaliatory campaign against the Mongols is not stated. As a result of the ineffectiveness of this campaign, it was noted that the aim was to ensure border security by supporting Yunus Khan brought from Shiraz. One cannot agree with the opinion of the author that Abu Sa'id sent Yunus Khan from Shiraz to his campaign in Azerbaijan so that Mongolia would not be destroyed. Because when Yunus Khan was summoned from Shiraz, the power of Mirza Sultan Abu Sa'id in Khorasan was weak, and he could not think about the Azerbaijan campaign.

S. Azimjonova emphasized that the Mongolian attacks were stopped as a result of Yunus Khan's seizure of the throne of Mongolia. The author focused on the conquest of Akhsini, one of the major cities of the Ferghana Valley, by another Timurid prince - Muhammad Joki, and the process of suppressing this rebellion. It was revealed that the appointment of Mirza Umarshaikh as governor of the Ferghana Valley was connected with this rebellion and its suppression. Also, the author notes that there is incorrect information about the date of the beginning of the governorship of Mirza Umarshaikh in the Fergana Valley, and correctly indicated that his governorship began in October 1462.

S. Azimjonova, before talking about the rule of Mirzo Umarshaikh, gave brief information about the cities and fortresses in the Fergana valley, relying on "Boburnoma". He noted that Akhsi fortress was further strengthened during the reign of Mirza Umarshaikh. At this point, the author touches upon the issue of Yunus Khan, who was fighting for the throne of Mongolia, regaining his throne with the help of Mirza Sultan Abu Sa'id for the second time. His opinions about the fact that after Yunus Khan won the throne of Mongolia, Mirza Sultan Abu Sa'id tried to conquer the Ferghana Valley while he was still alive, but these attempts were unsuccessful. Firstly, Yunus Khan, who became a full-fledged governor of Mongolia only in 1468-1469, did not have the opportunity for this. Secondly, if it were so, this incident would undoubtedly have been noticed by Mirza Haidar and Mirza Babur. Here, Abdurazzaq Samarkandi may have meant the robbery attack made by one of the Mongolian emirs, Ibrahim Bekchik, on the outskirts of Osh in 1465, during the internecine wars in Mongolia.

S. Azimjonova states that Mirza Umarshaikh wanted to fight for the throne of Samarkand with the help of Yunus Khan, Mirza gave Yunus Khan the cities of Akhsi, Osh and Margilan in the hope of getting help from the attack of Sultan Ahmed. These opinions, based on the information of Mirza Haidar and Mirza Babur, talk about the organized campaigns of Mirza Sultan Ahmed against Mirza Umarshaikh. But the author notes that it was impossible to determine the dates of these marches.

Yunus Khan, who effectively used the conflict between Mirza Umarshaikh and Mirza Sultan Ahmad, writes that he captured the cities of Tashkent and Sayram, he emphasizes that Khoja Ahror Vali played an important role in the transfer of Tashkent region to the Mongols, and

concludes that the distribution of property in this way was in the interests of Khoja Ahror Vali. Historical sources have information that supports this opinion. It seems that Mirza Umarshaikh was unable to gain the support of the people of the oasis when he was holding Tashkent in his hands. This is evidenced by the fact that the governor of Khoja Ahror paid the tax of 250 thousand dinars due to the growing discontent of the people from his own fund and donated another 70 thousand dinars to Mirza Umarshaikh.

S.Azimjonova explained on the basis of historical sources that the transfer of Tashkent to the hands of Yunus Khan caused the dissatisfaction of Mirza Umarshaikh and Mirza Sultan Ahmed, and their attempts to return this property to the control of the Timurids ended ineffectively. Mirza pointed out that Umarshaikh, who took advantage of Sultan Ahmed's defeat of the Mongols along the Chirchik River, captured the region of Oratepa. He noted that the governor of Ferghana had a strong military power, and that is why in 1394 Mirza Sultan Ahmed and Sultan Mahmud Khan invaded the valley in alliance.

At the end of this chapter, S.Azimjonova gives general conclusions about the activities of Mirza Umarshaikh, that as the ruler of the valley, he could not stop internal conflicts, mutual wars had a negative effect on the country's economy, these problems intensified the invasion attacks of the Mongols, and his sudden death opened the way for new conflicts. notes.

M. Abduraimov's thesis on "Temur and Tokhtamysh", which was defended at the Leningrad Institute of Oriental Studies in 1948, was published under the same name during the years of independence. In this work, the author also paid attention to the management system established by Amir Temur in Movarounnahr and the transfer of Ferghana to Mirza Umarshaikh [8].

A. Juvonmardiev's work "About land and water issues in Fergana in the XVI-XIX centuries", although it is related to the history of the period after the Timurids, the author cited some sources related to the economic life of the Timurid period[9].

In the studies of N. Mahmudov, B. G'. Gafurov, O. D. Chekhovich, issues related to the socio-economic history of the Timurid period were studied, and some notes on the history of the valley are found in them [10].

Фойдаланилган манба ва адабиётлар:

- 1.Шамукарамова Ф. Изучение истории государства Амира Темура и Темуридов конце XIX – начале XX вв. // Очерки истории государственности Узбекистана. Том 2. / Отв. Ред. Д. Алимова. – Т.: «Navro'z», 2018. – С. 57-74.
- 2.Татишчев В.Н. История Российская. Т. V. – М.Л., 1965. – С. 182-197; Карамзин Н.М.История государства Российского. Т. V. – Тула, 1990. – С.253 -295; Грановский Т.Н. Тимур // Полное собрание сочинений, Том 1. –СПб, 1905. – С. 341-352; Соловьев С.М. История России с древнейших времен. Том 4. – М., 1960. – С. 360-362.
- 3.Ivanin M. Two great generals. Genghis Khan and Amir Temur. - Т.:Fan, 1994. - 240 b (in the following places - Ivanin M. Ikki great commanders.);
- 4.Богданов М.Г. Последние дни жизни Тамерлана. Его поход на Китай (с персидского). // Туркестанские ведомости. 1872. № 18; Лидский С. Великие завоеватели Средней Азии: Александр Двурогий и Тимур Хромой. // Туркестанские ведомости. – 1889. №5,6; Павлов Н.Г. Тимур. // Павлов Н.Г. История Туркестана в связи с историческим очерком сопредельных стран (Персии, Афганистана Белуджистана, Индии и Восточного

Туркестана). – Т., 1910. – С. 12-16; Зимин Л.А. Четвертый поход Тимура на Хорезм. // Туркестанские ведомости. 1910. №.266; ўша муаллиф. Подробности смерти Тимура. // Протоколы заседаний и сообщения членов Туркестанского кружка любителей археологии, Год XIX, Вып I. Т., 1914. – С. 37-55.

5.Бартольд В.В. Очерк истории Семиречья. // Сочинения, Т.2, Ч.1. – М.:Издательство восточной литературы, 1963. – С. 21-106 (кейинги ўринларда – Бартольд В.В. Очерк истории Семиречья.); ўша муаллиф. Улугбек и его время. // Сочинения, Т.2, Ч.2. – М.: Наука, 1964. – С. 25-197 (кейинги ўринларда – Бартольд В.В. Улугбек и его время.); ўша муаллиф. К истории орошения Туркестана. // Сочинения, Т.3. – М.: Наука, 1965. – С. 97-237 (кейинги ўринларда – Бартольд В.В. К истории орошения Туркестана.).

6. Yakubovsky A.Yu. State of Timur. // History of the Uzbek SSR. I roof. The first book. - B. 352, 360-361; Yakubovsky A.Yu. Movarounnahr and Khurasan during the Timurid period. // History of the Uzbek SSR. I roof. The first book. - B. 371, 373-374, 388-389, 394-395; For more information, see Usmanov B. The figure of Amir Temur in Russian historiography. - T.: Science. - B. 94-96; Begimkulova L. A. Yu. Yakubovsky about the Timurid era of Ferghana. // Proceedings of the international scientific conference on "History of the Fergana Valley in new studies". - Scientific publication. – Fergana: FSU, 2019. – B. 136-139.

7. Mominov I. Amir Temur's place and role in the history of Central Asia. Based on written sources (second edition) - T.: Fan, 1993. - 56 p.

8.Азимджанова С. К истории Ферганы второй половины XV в. – Т.: Издательство Академии наук Узбекской ССР. 1957. – 92 с (in the following places – Азимджанова С. К истории Ферганы второй половины XV в.).

9.Abduraimov M. Temur and Tokhtamysh. - 80 p

10. Juvonmardiev A. About land and water issues in Ferghana in the 16th - 19th centuries - T.: Fan, 1965. - 182 p.

11.Махмудов Н. Их истории земельных отношений и налоговой политики Тимуридов. // Известия АН Таджикской ССР. Сер. Общ. Наук. I (32), Душанбе,1960, № 4; Махмудов Н. Земледелие и аграрные отношения в Средней Азии в XIV – XV вв. – Душанбе, 1966; Махмудов Н. Феодалная рента и налоги при Тимуре и Тимуридах // Труды Таджикского государственного университета. Сер. Ист. Наук, Вып. 2. Душанбе, 1967. – С. 231-270; Гафуров Б.Г. Таджикский народ в государстве Тимура и Тимуридов. // Гафуров Б.Г. Таджики. Древнейшая, древняя и средневековая историяю – М., 1972. – С. 476 – 517; Чехович О.Д. Тимуриды в освещении агиографических источников, неизвестных В.В. Бартольду и роль шайхов. // Бартольдские чтения. Тезисы докладов и сообщений. – М., 1974. – С. 58-61.